

Supporting Information

Ethanol solvation of polymer contamination in graphene solution-gated field effect transistors

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1. XPS análisis

Figure S1. Deconvoluted C1s core levels and survey spectra respectively for epoxy resin SU-8 (a and d), epoxy resin AZ (b and e) and PMMA (c and f).

Figure S2. Survey spectra and deconvoluted C1s Core levels respectively of macrotransistor a, b) before and c, d) after 10 min EtOH treatment.

Figure S3. Survey spectra and deconvoluted C1s Core levels respectively of macrotransistor a, b) before and c, d) after 2 h EtOH treatment.

Figure S4. Survey spectra and deconvoluted C1s Core levels respectively of macrotransistor a, b) before and c, d) after 10 min THF treatment.

Figure S5. Survey spectra and deconvoluted C1s Core levels respectively of macrotransistor a, b) before and c, d) after 2h THF treatment.

2. AFM analysis

Figure S6. AFM images of graphene surface on a macrotransistor a, b) before and d, e) after cleaning process with EtOH 10 min at different magnifications. AFM height profiles c) before and f) after cleaning process with EtOH 10 min (blue lines in b and e images respectively).

Figure S7. AFM images of graphene surface on a macrotransistor a, b) before and d, e) after cleaning process with EtOH 2h min at different magnifications. AFM height profiles c) before and f) after cleaning process with EtOH 2h min (blue lines in b and e images respectively).

Figure S8. AFM images of graphene surface on a macrotransistor a, b) before and d, e) after cleaning process with THF 10 min at different magnifications. AFM height profiles c) before and f) after cleaning process with THF 10 min (blue lines in b and e images respectively).

Figure S9. AFM images of graphene surface on a macrotransistor a, b) before and d, e) after cleaning process with THF 2h min at different magnifications. AFM height profiles c) before and f) after cleaning process with THF 2h min (blue lines in b and e images respectively).

Figure S10. Histogram of heights obtained from the figures S7-S10 50 μm^2 AFM images for macrotransistors before and after treatment with EtOH and THF.

Figure S11. AFM image of graphene surface on a macrotransistor a) detachment detail and b) profile after 10 min THF treatment.

3. Raman analysis

Figure S12. Averaged Raman spectra (≈ 1000 single-point spectra, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 532\text{nm}$ in $30 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$ area before and after cleaning process of macrotransistor with THF 10 min.

Figure S13. Averaged Raman spectra (≈ 1000 single-point spectra, $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 532\text{nm}$ in $30 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$ area before and after cleaning process of macrotransistor with THF 2h.

4. Summary tables

Table S1. Atomic percentage obtained by XPS analysis for the different macrotransistors before and after cleaning by different treatment conditions.

Treatment (Solvent/time)	C / at%			O / at%			Si / at%		
	Before	After	Δ	Before	After	Δ	Before	After	Δ
<i>EtOH/10 min</i>	54.85	50.59	4.36	27.61	28.18	-0.57	17.54	21.24	-3.7
<i>EtOH/2 h</i>	49.13	42.83	6.30	30.87	32.44	-1.57	20.00	24.73	-4.73
<i>THF/10 min</i>	64.34	60.85	3.49	19.84	22.23	-2.39	15.83	16.92	-1.09
<i>THF/2 h</i>	55.89	53.00	2.89	24.80	26.34	-1.54	26.34	20.66	-1.35

Table S2. C1s components for the different macrotransistors before and after cleaning by different treatment conditions.

Treatment (Solvent/time)	C1s component	Position / eV		At. ratio / %		
		Before	After	Before	After	Δ
<i>EtOH/10 min</i>	C=C	284.37	284.37	82.23	85.08	-2.85
	C-O	286.51	286.49	6.36	5.99	0.37
	C=O	287.73	287.78	4.20	4.27	-0.07
	O-C=O	288.81	288.79	7.22	4.66	2.56
	pi-pi*	-	-	-	-	-
<i>EtOH/2 h</i>	C=C	284.37	284.37	77.21	80.93	-3.72
	C-O	286.33	286.28	9.29	8.51	0.78
	C=O	287.57	287.48	5.42	5.09	0.33
	O-C=O	288.85	288.77	8.08	5.47	2.61
	pi-pi*	-	-	-	-	-
<i>THF/10 min</i>	C=C	284.37	284.37	93.64	90.13	3.51
	C-O	286.53	286.45	2.75	5.18	-2.43
	C=O	288.77	288.41	3.14	3.63	-0.49
	O-C=O	-	-	-	-	-
	pi-pi*	290.78	290.78	0.47	1.05	-0.58
<i>THF/2 h</i>	C=C	284.37	284.37	92.88	87.80	5.08
	C-O	286.47	286.47	2.81	5.86	-3.05
	C=O	288.78	288.45	2.67	4.01	-1.34
	O-C=O	-	-	-	-	-
	pi-pi*	290.78	290.78	1.64	2.33	-0.69

Table S3. AFM roughness for the different macrotransistors before and after cleaning by different treatment conditions.

Treatment (Solvent/time)	AFM roughness /nm		
	Before	After	Δ (before-after)
<i>EtOH/10 min</i>	2.03	1.66	0.37
<i>EtOH/2h</i>	3.07	1.18	1.89
<i>THF/10 min</i>	-	-	-
<i>THF/2h</i>	2.38	1.17	1.21

Table S4. I_{2D}/I_G of graphene in macrotransistors before and after cleaning by different treatment conditions.

Treatment (Solvent/time)	Transistor dimension	I_{2D}/I_G		
		Before	After	Δ (after-before)
<i>THF/10 min</i>	Macrotransistor	1.40	1.31	-0.09
<i>THF/2h</i>	Macrotransistor	1.30	1.38	0.08
<i>EtOH/10 min</i>	Macrotransistor	1.95	2.66	0.71
<i>EtOH/2h</i>	Macrotransistor	1.73	1.92	0.19
<i>EtOH/1h</i>	Microtransistor	1.83	1.86	0.06

5. Electrical evaluation of microtransistors before and after THF treatment.

a)

b)

Figure S14. Boxplots of G_m (transconductance) from the different microtransistors.

Figure S15. Transistors contacts image: left before THF treatment, right after THF treatment with detachment of the polymer passivation on the contact area. (Different transistor design from the described in the experimental section)

6. Comparative Table of graphene cleaning methodologies.

Table S5. I_{2D}/I_G of graphene in macrotransistors before and after cleaning by different treatment conditions.

Type	Advantage	Disadvantage	REF
Mechanical Cleaning (tip AFM)	Very effective	Costly, non-scalable (only small areas)	[1]
Current Induce desorption	Effective	Non-scalable (one device at a time)	[2]
Exposure to ozone	Scalable	Damage graphene	[3]
Exposure to plasma	Scalable	Damage graphene	[4]
High temperature annealing	Effective	Very Aggressive to graphene lattice	[5]
Electrostatic force	Effective	Very Aggressive to graphene lattice	[6]
Solvents: Dimethylacetamide	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient	Harsh solvents: toxic to health and environment	[7]
Solvents: Dioxolane	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient	Harsh solvents: toxic to health and environment	[8]
Solvents: 2-propanol	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient	Not fully polymer removal	[9]
Solvents: Acetone	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient	Leave organic residues	[9]
Solvents: NMP	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient, very effective	Not fully compatible with passivation layers, adsorption on graphene lattice	[10]
Solvents: Methanol	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient	Polymer cracking possible affectation Graphene lattice	[11,12]
Solvent THF	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient, very effective	Affectation integrity graphene lattice and passivation layer	This work
Solvent Ethanol	Simple, scalable, cost-efficient, very effective, environmentally friendly, safe, green solvent	Needs further studies with other polymers	This work

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